

Effect of Ply Blocking on Interlaminar Fracture in CFRP

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ABSTRACT

The failure of composites can be strongly dependant on the grouping together of adjacent plies of similar orientation (block size). In our study we examine the nature of the interlaminar stresses and how they effect the dominant fracture mechanisms within the structure. Interlaminar failure was ensured by inserting artificial damage into the specimens to initiate ply cracks. The results demonstrate the degree of blocking which may be tolerated in CFRP laminates while maintaining an acceptable degree of load carrying capacity and the effect of the overlap distance between the transverse ply cracks.

1. INTRODUCTION

In a cross-ply laminate under loading ply cracks appear parallel to the fibres in the transverse ply long before ultimate laminate failure. The origins of these ply cracks are believed to be inherent defects such as voids, microcracks, debonded fibre-matrix interfaces and broken fibres. As the stress increases, these defects act as local stress raisers, which grow and coalesce to form a through thickness flaw. Since the matrix and interface are much weaker than the fibre, these flaws always propagate through the matrix and interface while being parallel to the fibres.

It has long been noted that in composite laminates which exhibit delamination failure there is often accompanied ply cracking of the matrix parallel to the direction of the fibres. Indeed this ply cracking can, in many cases, be seen to initiate the process of delamination between the plies, or ply blocks. This has been widely reported in work with notched laminates and mechanically fastened joints.

In a pin loaded joint consisting only of 0° and 90° CFRP layers ply cracks will occur at the points of maximum hoop stress. It is also common to observe ply cracks which initiate due to shear loading at points of high stress gradients. These cracks will grow through the ply as load is increased until they meet the interface with the adjacent orthogonal ply. At this point the strain energy available will not be enough to carry on through into the next ply (as this would require

fibre fracture). However, the crack may continue by effectively turning through 90° to form an interlaminar crack as we require much less strain energy to fracture this weak matrix layer.

Depending on the ratio of the load required to produce a ply crack (L_p) to that required for delamination (L_D) determines whether the so called 'first ply failure' of a lamina determines the overall strength of the laminate or whether further load may be sustained after ply fracture. Hence, if $L_p \geq L_D$ first ply failure will prove critical. However if $L_p < L_D$ the joint will be able to sustain further loading subsequent to ply cracking until delamination occurs. This theory is displayed graphically in Figure 1. Hence in order to determine the nature of the failure of such joints we must analyse the factors affecting the matrix strength both parallel to the fibres within a ply and between adjacent plies in the interlaminar region.

Extensive research, both theoretical and experimental, has been carried out on the problem of transverse ply cracking in an effort to understand the behaviour of laminates after first ply failure. These investigations have been split into to broad areas, covering the failure analysis of transverse ply crack initiation, propagation and multiplication, as well as studies which concentrate on the laminate property degradation.

Numerous also papers exist on the prediction of delamination growth at sites of impact damage, straight free edges and notches. Recent work by Whitcomb (1) has also emerged on the prediction of delamination growth from ply cracks in cross-ply laminates.

In our investigation we concentrate on the effect of ply blocking and the length of delamination on the strength of the laminate. We analyse the probable effects of ply blocking on cross-ply laminates by the use of a basic uniaxial tensile specimen containing artificial damage which provides us with a simple model which may be extended to more complex structures.

Figure 1. Prediction of Blocked Laminate Failure

2. SPECIMEN CONFIGURATION

The specimens (as shown in Figure 2) were manufactured in 32 ply, 4mm thick plates from unidirectional (0°) T300 913 in a hot press moulding operation. They were then machined to 12.8mm wide and 254mm long. During lay-up cuts were inserted in the laminae in symmetrical blocking sequences and at varying overlaps. The specimens were tested with aluminium end tabs. Four block sizes 'b' were tested 1mm, 0.5mm, 0.25mm, 0.125mm each with three different overlap lengths 5mm, 10mm, 20mm.

Figure 2. The Blocked Specimens

3. ANALYSIS

The easiest specimen to analyse is the three block specimen, which can effectively be thought of as a double butt-strap joint or, once the ply cracks have occurred, as a double lap joint. We may think of the ply blocks as the adherend and the interlaminar zone as an adhesive layer. Hence, this may give us an indication of the expected stress distributions and failure mechanisms of the specimen.

Adams et al (2) demonstrated that for a double lap joint with a range of adhesives there was an increase in strength with overlap until a plateau of maximum strength was reached (at about 15mm), after which any increases in overlap distance would have no effect on joint strength. It would be reasonable to assume that such a relationship should also occur in our specimens.

The stresses applied to a double lap joint do not only produce shear loading on the adhesive layer but also other stresses which result in tensile forces being exerted on the adhesive. Although there is no net bending moment on a symmetrical double lap joint because the load is applied through the adhesive to the adherend away from their own neutral axes, the double lap joint experiences internal bending (as shown in Figure 3). In a symmetrical double lap, the centre adherend experiences no net bending moment, but the outer adherends bend, giving rise to tensile stresses across the adhesive layer at the end of the overlap where they are not loaded. Therefore we would expect the interlaminar fracture to consist of a significant amount of mode 1 fracture as well as mode 2, hence our analysis should take account of this kind of mixed mode loading.

Figure 3. Induced Moments in a Double Lap Joint

Two approaches to predict failure of the specimens were undertaken. One analysis uses a directly applied, closed form fracture mechanics technique developed by Nairn (3) is used. In the second approach we employ a two-dimensional finite element model in conjunction with a fracture mechanics method to predict stable delamination growth as proposed by Rybicki et al (4) to establish strain energy release rates. In both approaches it is assumed that failure occurs when the outermost block delaminates and that the matrix filled, artificial ply crack region contributes little to the laminate strength and can effectively be ignored, and hence an initial ply crack is assumed.

The material constants used for the analyses were as follows;

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 E_{11}: & 140 \text{ GPa} & G_{Ic}: & 188 \text{ Jm}^{-2} \\
 E_{22}: & 8.5 \text{ GPa} & G_{IIc}: & 416 \text{ Jm}^{-2} \\
 G_{12}: & 4.5 \text{ GPa} & & \\
 \nu_{12}: & 0.35 & &
 \end{array}$$

Figure 4. Closed Form Fracture Model

3.1. Closed Form Solution

3.1.1 Analysis Mode 2 Delamination

Using the laminate model shown in Figure 4 and taking the grips to be parallel with no induced moments we will first of all assume the case in which all fracture is mode 2. Hence from the equation of the total strain energy release rate for the self-similar propagation of a delamination crack under general axial loading, which may be expressed as,

$$G = \frac{a_{11}}{4BA} \left[\frac{P_1^2}{\xi} + \frac{P_2^2}{(1-\xi)} - (P_1 + P_2)^2 \right], \quad (1)$$

where $P_1 + P_2$ is the total loading on the laminate, P_1 being the loading on the section of the laminate above the delamination and P_2 is the loading on the section below the delamination. B is the breadth of the specimen, A is the cross sectional area and ξ is the ratio of the depth through the thickness to the delamination to the overall thickness. For the case shown in Figure 4, we have $P_1=0$ and $P_2 = P$, hence Equation (1) reduces to,

$$G_{II} = \frac{a_{11}P^2}{4BA} \left(\frac{1}{1-\xi} - 1 \right). \quad (2)$$

Introducing the calibration factor Y^2 (a/w), where, from Figure 6, a is the depth of the ply crack, or the block thickness (b) and w is the laminate thickness ($2h$) we obtain,

$$G_{II} = \frac{Y^2 P^2 a}{4B^2 h^2 E_{11}}, \quad (3)$$

Nairn (3) gives a solution for the calibration factor from the shear lag model which includes a correction for the local stress field effects unlike the equation above which relies on the assumption that the delamination front is far enough away from the ply crack as to be unaffected by its presence. For large delamination lengths the Nairn solution states that the value for Y^2 tends toward,

$$Y^2 = \frac{1}{2(1 - a/2h)} \quad (4)$$

Hence, the load at which the model predicts delamination (doubling due to the use of half model) can simply be obtained by substituting the critical value of mode 2 strain energy release rate in to equation (3) and rearranging,

$$P_{Ic} = 2 \left(\frac{4G_{IIc} E_{11} B^2 h^2}{Y^2 a} \right)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

3.1.2 Analysis for Mode 1 Delamination

In this analysis we shall again look only at the outer block and this time apply a quasi-DCB type analysis. Hence presenting the general loading case of two equal and opposite moments being applied through the mid-point of a beam, producing a pure mode 1 (opening mode) fracture we have,

$$G_I = \frac{12M^2}{E_{11} B^2 h^3} \quad (6)$$

Then failure load may simply be expressed as,

$$P_{Ic} = \left(\frac{G_{Ic} E_{11} B^2 b^3}{12x^2} \right) \left(\frac{2h}{b} \right), \quad (7)$$

where, $x=b/2$.

3.2. Finite Element Analysis

A two-dimensional finite element model as shown in Figure 5 was constructed using 8 noded isoparametric elements. The model uses a technique developed by Rybicki et al (4) to calculate the values of strain energy release rates. This method requires two runs of the program (see Figure 6). In the first run no delamination crack is present and the forces in the x and y directions at the nodes along which the delamination will run are noted. In the next run these nodes are released and their displacements in the x and y directions are measured. Fracture mechanics is then used defining mode 1 and 2. Hence,

$$G_I = \frac{1}{2LBP^2} [F_{yb}(\delta_{yd} - \delta_{yb}) + F_{yc}(\delta_{ye} - \delta_{yc})], \quad (6)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{1}{2LBP^2} [F_{xb}(\delta_{xd} - \delta_{xb}) + F_{xc}(\delta_{xe} - \delta_{xc})], \quad (7)$$

therefore if we apply a unit load to the model we can calculate the load at failure in purely mode 1 fracture by,

$$P_{Ic} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{G_{Ic}}{G_I}\right)}, \quad (8)$$

and for a purely mode 2 failure,

$$P_{IIc} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{G_{IIc}}{G_{II}}}\right)}. \quad (9)$$

Figure 5. Finite Element Model

Figure 6. Finite Element Calculation of Strain Energy Release Rates

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the closed form fracture mechanics solution, the finite element analysis and the experimental analysis are outlined in Figures 7 & 8 displaying the effect of ply blocking on the failure load. The graphs show the failure load of a specimen if fracture was to occur without delamination and instead the ply crack was to propagate through the fibres. At the bottom of the graph in Figure 8 we also illustrate the failure load of a specimen which contained no overlap of

blocks, in which case the failure load would be simply that of the resin in tension. All of the curves display the effect of reducing the block size can have on the laminate strength. We observe an initial sharp increase which will plateau to a maximum value, at which we observe a change from totally delamination dominated failure to a failure which includes some fibre fracture. Hence, the ability to predict the experimental curve plotted in Figure 7 would prove very useful in laminate design.

We can see that the failure loads predicted by the mode 2 closed form solution are in good agreement with the experimental results, especially as the overlap distance increases. However, if we take into account the effects of mixed mode loading we are presented with failure loads which are considerably lower than those measured experimentally. This may be due to the effect of the matrix in the ply crack is created, in our model we assume a ply crack is already present before any loading is applied. There may also be stress relieving mechanisms during fracture which are not accounted for in the model. The very low values for the mode 1 failure loads do, however, seem to imply that the use of the simple DCB approach may have to be modified.

The FE results displayed in Figure 7 exhibit low failure loads in comparison with the experiment. Again this may be a result of the assumption of a perfect ply crack whereas in practice a resin filled region is present. Current FE analyses are being performed to account for the matrix filled cracks. Preliminary results suggest more promising agreement with experimental results.

The results for the failure load against overlap demonstrate, as expected, a relationship similar to that exhibited in the work of Adams et al (2) for double lap joints. The results show that the failure load will only increase to a certain level at which point no further increase in strength may be obtained. This level was judged to be around 20mm.

Figure 8. Test Failure Loads of Blocked Specimen vs Overlap Distance

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

We have demonstrated from experimental analysis that the blocking together of large numbers of plies in CFRP can prove detrimental to laminate strength when failure occurs due to interlaminar fracture. Further we have shown that the delamination length in the direction of loading (the overlap length) is also significant in reducing the strength of the specimen for lengths of under 20mm. Prediction of specimen failure loads with the use of a mode 2 only closed form fracture criterion yielded results close to that of the experimental results. The finite element predictions of failure load were conservative. With further development this type of approach appears could be as a useful design tool, if not to predict precise failure loads then to give an indication of the relationship between laminate strength and block thickness, hence, supplying the engineer with useful information on the degree of ply blocking for efficient laminate design.

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